

Deliverable No. 2.2

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FarFish

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Deliverable D2.2

Data Management Plan under the H2020 Open Research Data Pilot

21/03/2022

Executive Summary

The overall goal of WP2 in the FarFish project is to "*advance knowledge and collate data related to biological characteristics of the main fish stocks in the selected fisheries, and to evaluate the appropriateness, relevance and applicability of stock assessment models currently in use for these fisheries*", as presented in the project description (DoA).

Task 2.2 and deliverable 2.2 contributes towards these goals by creating a "*Data Management Plan*" (DMP), in accordance with the Horizon 2020 Open Research Data Pilot. The DMP was initially developed in the first months of the project and was first published in month six (November 2017) of the project. The DMP has been regularly updated during the lifetime of the project and this is the fifth, and final (revised), version. The DMP contains 47 forms detailing the content of all datasets used within FarFish, how it will be preserved, and steps taken to make data publically available after the project end.

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1 Revision history

Table 1 Revision history

Version	Date	Revised by	Comment
V0.1	08.11.2017	PBS	Draft deliverable
V1.0	29.11.2017	PBS	Completed deliverable
V2.0	28.11.2018	PBS	M18 Periodic update <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Added 22 new forms – no updates to existing forms Updated the format for all existing forms
V3.0	25.05.2020	PBS	M36 Periodic update <ul style="list-style-type: none"> One new form added (p.47) Minor revision to certain forms (time period covered (p. 9/10/46) and dataset owner (p. 15))
Final	25.11.2021	CBO	Final update <ul style="list-style-type: none"> 5 forms added (p.30, 35, 43-45) 3 forms removed, replaced by 2 others (p.39-40) 2 forms removed, replaced by 2 others (p.41-42) 13 forms updated with links to Zenodo Change of participant name from Syntesa to Sjukovin
Revision	21.03.2022	CBO	Addition requested: Data collection on small pelagics and environmental forcing on the west coast of Africa, information on small pelagics for Morocco, and environmental data <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Small pelagic dataset for stock assessment in the Moroccan Atlantic coast (UCA) p.42 Environmental (hydrodynamic) conditions on the NW African coast from 3D reanalysis models (CSIC) p.53 Environmental (biogeochemical) conditions on the NW African coast from 3D reanalysis models (CSIC) p.54 Environmental (oxygen) conditions on the NW African coast from 3D reanalysis models (CSIC) p.55 Two fish in a pod. Data from a self-sampling pilot program to separate between black hake species in W-Africa (CCMAR) p.58

2 Introduction

Over the course of a research project, considerable amounts of data are gathered. Often, these data are not preserved or made available for reuse later on, causing time and effort to be spent in other projects gathering similar data. The goal of the Horizon 2020 Open Research Data Pilot is remedy this issue, by ensuring that research data generated through a project is made available for reuse after a projects end. The H2020 Open Research Data Pilot is based on the principle of making data FAIR:

- Findable
- Accessible
- Interoperable
- Reusable

As a way of managing the data used during a project lifetime, a Data Management Plan (DMP) must be created. The DMP-forms includes details on:

- the handling of research data during and after the end of the project
- what data will be collected, processed and/or generated
- which methodology and standards will be applied
- whether data will be shared/made open access
- how data will be curated and preserved (including after the end of the project)
- ethical issues related to the data
- estimated costs associated with data archiving/sharing

The creation of the DMP is the responsibility of task 2.2/deliverable 2.2. As per the DoA, task 2.2 will fulfill three requirements as a participant in the H2020 Open Research Data Pilot: "*Firstly, the collected research data should be deposited in data repository (...). Secondly, the project will have to take measures to enable third parties to access, mine, exploit, reproduce and disseminate this research data. Finally, a Data Management Plan (DMP) has to be developed detailing what kind of data the project is expected to generate, whether and how it will be exploited or made accessible for verification and reuse, and how it will be curated and preserved*".

3 Method

In order to collect information from the project participants, a form and an explanation describing the desired content of each DMP-component was sent out to all partners by email (both are attached in "*Appendix 2 – Templates*"). Detailed instructions on how to fill out the form was included in the accompanying e-mail. Both the form and the explanation were based on the proposed DMP-structure in "*Guidelines on FAIR Data Management in Horizon 2020*" (2016). Along with the two forms, an example from a previous project was distributed in the same email.

In order to harmonize the forms, the formatting of certain forms have been edited where needed. No changes have ben made to the content.

4 Conclusion

The deliverable contains 47 forms, detailing the content of the different datasets, the ways in which data will be stored and how/if it is made publically available. The forms are grouped according to case study. Datasets not pertaining to one individual case study are grouped in a separate category: "*Non-case study specific*". If no case study-specific datasets have been submitted for a particular case study, the case study is not included in the list in the appendix.

The DMP is intended to be a "living" document, and evolve as the project progresses. Periodic revisions of the DMP were planned once within each 18-month periodic reporting period. Ahead of each periodic review, an email was sent out to all project participants, asking them to update the DMP-forms pertaining to their datasets by either editing existing information or by adding new forms if necessary. The Table 0 "Revision history" provides a summary of revisions carried out over the lifetime of this Data Management Plan. It provides a version number, the date of the latest revision, the initials of the editor, and a comment describing the changes made.

To ensure the long time storage of the datasets after the project end, a FarFish account has been created on the public repository [Zenodo](https://zenodo.org)^{*}. Datasets are divided into two categories: research data produced or collected for the FarFish project (25 datasets) and minutes and reports from the Joint Committee meetings (22 datasets). While the latter are closed, the 25 research datasets, with the exception of one due to confidentiality reasons, are open. Three of the research datasets are reports, for those the link to the report is provided. The 17 remaining have been uploaded on Zenodo. An overview of the 25 research datasets is provided in table 2 while table 3 gives an overview of the 22 other ones.

With the exception of personal information collected during interviews, the potential for ethical issues raised by FarFish are relatively minor, though this might vary from dataset to dataset. Participation in the project is on a voluntarily basis, and participants have the right to limit the use of any information they provide and may request that information collected is deleted at the end of the project. FarFish follows the Eurostat rules and national guidelines on data confidentiality, and the ICC/ESOMAR International Code on Market, Opinion and Social Research and Data Analytics. See the "Ethics and Security" section in the DoA for more information.

* <https://zenodo.org/communities/farfish2020?page=1&size=20>

Table 2 Overview of the research datasets with hyperlinks to the datasets in the Appendix and external links to the data

CSs	Dataset owner	Dataset title	Links to the dataset
Seychelles	SFA	IndustrialPS Processed 0016: Purse Seine Fishery – Seychelles – Fishing vessels, Catch, effort, Length frequency, 2000-2019	https://zenodo.org/record/5525755
	SFA	IndustrialSV Data 0016: Supply Vessel – Seychelles – Fishing vessels and effort 2005-2018	https://zenodo.org/record/5525755
Senegal	COREWAM/CROD T-ISRA	Black hakes <i>Merluccius senegalensis</i> and <i>M. polli</i> scientific data surveys 2002-2016	https://zenodo.org/record/5710472#.YZZQY5rMKUk
Mauritania	UoP	Dataset for small pelagics value chain in Mauritania	https://zenodo.org/record/5702666#.YZOCc0bP3OQ
Cabo Verde	UoP	Dataset tuna value chains from the West African SFPAs	https://zenodo.org/record/5702645#.YZOEmEbP3OQ
South-East Atlantic	IMR	REPORT OF THE 12th SEAFO SCIENTIFIC COMMITTEE	http://www.seafo.org/media/4ca98f5f-c111-4bcf-875b-36ac3213b8b7/SEAFOweb/pdf/SC/open/eng/SC%20Report%202016_pdf
	IMR	REPORT OF THE 12th SEAFO SCIENTIFIC COMMITTEE	http://www.seafo.org/media/4ca98f5f-c111-4bcf-875b-36ac3213b8b7/SEAFOweb/pdf/SC/open/eng/SC%20Report%202016_pdf
South-West Atlantic	Sjokovin	Catches of three main species in the Southwest Atlantic area FAO 41 from FAO - FAO. 2020. Fishery and Aquaculture Statistics. Global capture production 1950-2018 (FishstatJ).	https://zenodo.org/record/5603362#.YXqZ_dbML0o
	Sjokovin	Trade data hake Southwest Atlantic	https://zenodo.org/record/5616246#.YXvpjkbMLOQ
	Sjokovin	Catches of Argentine hake patagonian stock in the Southwest Atlantic	https://zenodo.org/record/5616472#.YXvpYUbmLOQ
Moroccan Atlantic coast	UCA	Small pelagic dataset for stock assessment in the Moroccan Atlantic coast	https://zenodo.org/record/6371237-.YjcochDMKdY
Non cs specific	Nofima	STECF Economic data for Purse seiners and hook vessels 2015 2018	https://zenodo.org/record/5607123#.YX-5yRrMKUk
	Nofima	Data on EU vessel tuna catches in ICCAT by 5 degree gridcells in 2018	https://zenodo.org/record/5607123#.YX-5yRrMKUk
	Nofima	Export quantity of fish meal and fish oil from Mauritania 2010 2020	https://zenodo.org/record/5607086#.YX-6HxrMKUk
	Nofima	Tuna exports west africa 2014 2019 FishstatJ	https://zenodo.org/record/5539861
	Nofima	Tuna imports EU west africa 2015 2019	https://zenodo.org/record/5539855

	Nofima	<i><u>DG MARE – SFPA Evaluation reports</u></i>	https://ec.europa.eu/fisheries/documentation/studies .
	CSIC	<i><u>Model outputs an indicators – Data summary, estimates and projections</u></i>	https://zenodo.org/record/5541269
	CSIC	<i><u>Historical Fisheries data – Catches/survey time series</u></i>	https://zenodo.org/record/5541279
	CSIC	<i><u>Biological fisheries data – Maturity, growth, mortality</u></i>	https://zenodo.org/record/5541281
	CSIC	<i><u>Decision Support and visualisation tools outputs</u></i>	https://zenodo.org/record/5541290
	CSIC	<i><u>Environmental (hydrodynamic) conditions on the NW African coast from 3D reanalysis models</u></i>	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6378537
	CSIC	<i><u>Environmental (biogeochemical) conditions on the NW African coast from 3D reanalysis models</u></i>	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6378807
	CSIC	<i><u>Environmental (oxygen) conditions on the NW African coast from 3D reanalysis models</u></i>	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6378818
	CCMAR	<i><u>Two fish in a pod. Data from a self-sampling pilot program to separate between black hake species in W-Africa</u></i>	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6363365

 Closed du to confidentiality reasons.

Table 3 Overview of the minutes and reports from the Joint Committee meetings

CSs	Dataset owner	Dataset title
Seychelles	Matis	<i>Minutes from joint committee meeting for the Seychelles SFPA, held in Victoria 30 June – 1 July 2016</i>
	Matis	<i>Minutes from joint committee meeting for the Seychelles SFPA, held in Brussels 3-4 May 2017.</i>
	Matis	<i>Minutes from joint committee meeting for the Seychelles SFPA, held in Brussels 10 February 2015.</i>
Senegal	Matis	<i>Minutes from joint committee meeting for the Senegalese SFPA, held in Dakar 15-17 April 2015</i>
	Matis	<i>List of financial support from EU to Senegal in 2014-2019 in connection with the SFPA and allocation to tasks.</i>
	Matis	<i>Minutes from joint committee meeting for the Senegalese SFPA, held in Brussels 19-29 April 2016</i>
	Matis	<i>Minutes from joint committee meeting for the Senegalese SFPA, held in Dakar 10-12 April 2017.</i>
	Matis	<i>Report of the joint committee for the Senegalese SFPA 2018.</i>
	Matis	<i>Report of the joint committee for the Senegalese SFPA 2016.</i>
	Matis	<i>Report of the joint committee for the Senegalese SFPA 2017.</i>
Mauritania	Matis	<i>Minutes from joint committee meeting for the Mauritanian SFPA, held in Brussels 30-31 May 2016</i>
	Matis	<i>Minutes from joint committee meeting for the Mauritanian SFPA, held in Brussels 20-22 September 2017.</i>
	Matis	<i>Report of the joint committee for the Mauritanian SFPA, for the period 2008-2012; 2013-2014 and 2015-2019. Report published in September 2017.</i>
	Matis	<i>Report of the joint committee for the Mauritanian SFPA 2016.</i>
	Matis	<i>Minutes from joint committee meeting for the Mauritanian SFPA, held in Nouakchott 15-16 November 2016.</i>
	Matis	<i>Report of the joint committee for the Mauritanian SFPA 2017.</i>
Cabo Verde	Matis	<i>Minutes from joint committee meeting for the Cabo Verde SFPA, held in Brussels 12 October 2018.</i>
	Matis	<i>Minutes from joint committee meeting for the Cabo Verde SFPA, held in Brussels 23-25 March 2015.</i>
	Matis	<i>Minutes from joint committee meeting for the Cabo Verde SFPA, held in Brussels 28-29 November 2017.</i>
	Matis	<i>Minutes from joint committee meeting for the Cabo Verde SFPA, held in Mindelo 11-13 May 2016.</i>
Non cs specific	Matis	<i>Catch reports by EU vessels in the SFPA of Seychelles, Mauritania, Cabo Verde and Senegal in 2014-2019</i>
	Matis	<i>Catch reports by EU vessels in non-EU waters in 2014-2019</i>

5 Acknowledgements

We wish to acknowledge the contribution of all project participants who contributed to the completion of this deliverable.

6 References

- "*Guidelines on FAIR Data Management in Horizon 2020*" – EC Directorate-General for Research and Innovation, version 3.0, July 26th 2016
- "*Guidelines on Open Access to Scientific Publications and Research Data in Horizon 2020*" – EC Directorate-General for Research and Innovation, version 3.1, August 25th 2016
- "*OpenAire: What is the Open Research Data Pilot*" – Accessed 31.10.2017:
<https://www.openaire.eu/what-is-the-open-research-data-pilot>.

7 Appendix

7.1 Appendix 1: Data management plans

7.1.1 Seychelles

1. Data set reference/name	<i>IndustrialPS_Processed_0016: Purse Seine Fishery – Seychelles – Fishing vessels, Catch, effort, Length frequency, 2000-2019</i> SFA
2. Data summary	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The purse seine fishery datasets contain information on all purse seiners (including EU vessels) licensed to operate within the Seychelles EEZ. Data are collected on vessels, catch by species, effort, geographical fishing area, length frequency, landing and transshipment. The data is gathered for scientific analysis, management and policy decision making purposes, for access payment and to meet obligations to international bodies (e.g IOTC, FAO etc) Data is collected from Fishing vessels (logbook), vessel agents (landing/transshipment), SFA technicians (length frequency) and is captured, processed and managed by the Seychelles Fishing Authority.
3. FAIR Data	
3.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The described sources uses standard nomenclature for statistical data as per SWIOFP Statbase metadata format. Data can be extracted from MS Access database into Excel- and CSV files A PDF report based on the data and containing the data is uploaded on Zenodo: https://zenodo.org/record/5525755
3.2 Making data openly accessible	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Project- generated data are shared in designated publication at the Flag level but not at individual vessel level for confidentiality reasons. Data are also available in public domain on IOTC website www.iotc.org Data not publicly available may be provided upon an official request. Data can be extracted from Ms Access and provided in requested format. Metadata is available in Ms Excel format
3.3 Making data interoperable	Data are interoperable. Metadata vocabularies are as per SWIOFP Statbase project.
3.4 Increase data re-use (through clarifying licences)	Published data are re-usable. Confidential data will be assessed on a case by case basis upon official request.
4. Allocation of resources	NA
5. Data security	Data reside on a secure server and is backed-up on a regularly basis.
6. Ethical aspects	NA
7. Other	SFA works in collaboration with our partners Institut de Recherche pour le Development (IRD)- France and Instituto Español de Oceanografía (IEO) for data management.

1. Data set reference/name	<i>IndustrialSV_Data_0016: Supply Vessel – Seychelles – Fishing vessels and effort 2005-2018</i> SFA
2. Data summary	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The Supply vessel dataset contain information on all supply vessel in the purse seine fishery (including EU vessels) licensed to operate within the Seychelles EEZ. Data are collected on vessels, effort and geographical operation area. • The data is gathered for management and policy decision making purposes, for scientific analysis and to meet obligations to international bodies (e.g IOTC, FAO etc) • Data is collected from Fishing vessels (logbook) and is captured, processed and managed by the Seychelles Fishing Authority.
3. FAIR Data	
3.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The described sources use standard nomenclature for statistical data as per SWIOFP Statbase metadata format. • Data can be extracted from MS Access database into Excel files and CSV files • A PDF report based on the data and containing the data is uploaded on Zenodo: https://zenodo.org/record/5525755
3.2 Making data openly accessible	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Project- generated data are shared in designated publication at the Flag level but not at individual vessel level for confidentiality reasons. • Data are also available in public domain on IOTC website www.iotc.org • Data not publicly available may be provided upon an official request. • Data can be extracted from Ms Access and provided in requested format. • Metadata is available in Ms Excel format
3.3 Making data interoperable	Data are interoperable Metadata vocabularies are as per SWIOFP Statbase project
3.4 Increase data re-use (through clarifying licences)	Published data are re-usable Confidential data will be assessed on a case by case basis upon official request.
4. Allocation of resources	NA
5. Data security	Data reside on a secure server and is backed-up on a regularly basis
6. Ethical aspects	NA
7. Other	SFA works in collaboration with our partners Institut de Recherche pour le Development (IRD)- France and Instituto Español de Oceanografía (IEO) for data management.

1. Data set reference/name	<i>Minutes from joint committee meeting for the Seychelles SFPA, held in Victoria 30 June – 1 July 2016</i> MATIS
2. Data summary	Minutes from joint committee meeting for the Seychelles SFPA in 2016
3. FAIR Data	
3.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata	The minutes are in pdf format and have been provided to FarFish by DG MARE with the conditions that they will not be made publicly available. The minutes are therefore stored in a password protected internal webpage of www.farfish.eu where only selected researchers are granted access.
3.2 Making data openly accessible	The data will not be made openly accessible
3.3 Making data interoperable	No efforts will be made to make the data interoperable.
3.4 Increase data re-use (through clarifying licences)	The minutes are only intended for internal use in FarFish.
4. Allocation of resources	No additional cost required.
5. Data security	Data security provided by the technical support of FarFish website.
6. Ethical aspects	No ethical aspects.
7. Other	NA

1. Data set reference/name	<i>Minutes from joint committee meeting for the Seychelles SFPA, held in Brussels 3-4 May 2017.</i> MATIS
2. Data summary	Minutes from joint committee meeting for the Seychelles SFPA in 2017
3. FAIR Data	
3.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata	The minutes are in pdf format and have been provided to FarFish by DG MARE with the conditions that they will not be made publicly available. The minutes are therefore stored in a password protected internal webpage of www.farfish.eu where only selected researchers are granted access.
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3.3 Making data interoperable	No efforts will be made to make the data interoperable.
3.4 Increase data re-use (through clarifying licences)	The minutes are only intended for internal use in FarFish.
4. Allocation of resources	No additional cost required.
5. Data security	Data security provided by the technical support of FarFish website.
6. Ethical aspects	No ethical aspects.
7. Other	NA

1. Data set reference/name	<i>Minutes from joint committee meeting for the Seychelles SFPA, held in Brussels 10 February 2015.</i> MATIS
2. Data summary	Minutes from joint committee meeting for the Seychelles SFPA in 2018
3. FAIR Data	
3.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata	The minutes are in pdf format and have been provided to FarFish by DG MARE with the conditions that they will not be made publicly available. The minutes are therefore stored in a password protected internal webpage of www.farfish.eu where only selected researchers are granted access.
3.2 Making data openly accessible	The data will not be made openly accessible
3.3 Making data interoperable	No efforts will be made to make the data interoperable.
3.4 Increase data re-use (through clarifying licences)	The minutes are only intended for internal use in FarFish.
4. Allocation of resources	No additional cost required.
5. Data security	Data security provided by the technical support of FarFish website.
6. Ethical aspects	No ethical aspects.
7. Other	NA

7.1.2 Senegal

Data set reference and name	<i>Black hakes Merluccius senegalensis and M. polli scientific data surveys 2002-2016</i> COREWAM/CRODT-ISRA
Data set summary	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The database consists of Senegalese black hakes <i>Merluccius senegalensis</i> and <i>M. polli</i> information originating from 8 scientific deep demersal surveys off Senegal between 2002 and 2016. • It's the first time for black hakes to be namely specified in such fisheries agreement between Senegal and other countries • Spanish and local fleets activities from the end of 1980's to 2016, bearing in mind that hake fisheries are irregularly performed by these fleets. E.g., due to failing of CPUE, there was a break from 2006 to 2014 • Artisanal canoes activities are anecdotic due to their low level catches
Making data findable, including provisions for metadata	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Scientific surveys and industrial data will not be openly available. They are uploaded in Zenodo in closed access: https://zenodo.org/record/5710472#.YZZQY5rMKUk • Black hakes data were extracted exclusively for that purpose from scientific surveys. Variables and related explanation are furnished for a better understanding and appropriation of data.
Making data openly accessible	The data are exchangeable between researchers in a suitable excel file sheet.
Making data interoperable	The data are reusable during the duration of the Farfish Project.
Data security	Data exist in CRODT/ISRA and are saved within different supports for a long term conservation.
Ethical aspects	Data are Senegalese property. They can be used under scientific authorisation from CRODT/ISRA in the context of FarFish.
Other	NA

1. Data set reference/name	<i>Minutes from joint committee meeting for the Senegalese SFPA, held in Dakar 15-17 April 2015</i> <i>(ACCORD DE PARTENARIAT DANS LE DOMAINE DE LA PECHE DURABLE ENTRE L'UNION EUROPEENNE ET LA REPUBLIQUE DU SENEGAL - liere session ordinaire de la Commission mixte – PROCESVERBAL)</i> MATIS
2. Data summary	Minutes from joint committee meeting for the Senegalese SFPA in 2015
3. FAIR Data	
3.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata	The minutes are in pdf format and have been provided to FarFish by DG MARE with the conditions that they will not be made publicly available. The minutes are therefore stored in a password protected internal webpage of www.farfish.eu where only selected researchers are granted access.
3.2 Making data openly accessible	The data will not be made openly accessible
3.3 Making data interoperable	No efforts will be made to make the data interoperable. If necessary the minutes might be translated from French to English.
3.4 Increase data re-use (through clarifying licences)	The minutes are only intended for internal use in FarFish.
4. Allocation of resources	No additional cost required.
5. Data security	Data security provided by the technical support of FarFish website.
6. Ethical aspects	No ethical aspects.
7. Other	NA

1. Data set reference/name	<i>List of financial support from EU to Senegal in 2014-2019 in connection with the SFPA and allocation to tasks.</i> <i>(APP Union européenne - Sénégal 2014-2019 MATRICE appui sectoriel)</i> MATIS
2. Data summary	List of financial support from EU to Senegal in 2014-2019 in connection with the SFPA and allocation to tasks.
3. FAIR Data	
3.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata	The data is in pdf format and have been provided to FarFish by DG MARE with the conditions that they will not be made publicly available. The data set is therefore stored in a password protected internal webpage of www.farfish.eu where only selected researchers are granted access.
3.2 Making data openly accessible	The data will not be made openly accessible
3.3 Making data interoperable	No efforts will be made to make the data interoperable. If necessary the data might be translated from French to English.
3.4 Increase data re-use (through clarifying licences)	The data is only intended for internal use in FarFish.
4. Allocation of resources	No additional cost required.
5. Data security	Data security provided by the technical support of FarFish website.
6. Ethical aspects	No ethical aspects.
7. Other	NA

1. Data set reference/name	<i>Minutes from joint committee meeting for the Senegalese SFPA, held in Brussels 19-29 April 2016</i> <i>(ACCORD DE PARTENARIAT DANS LE DOMAINE DE LA PECHE DURABLE ENTRE L'UNION EUROPEENNE ET LA REPUBLIQUE DU SENEGAL - 2^{ème} session ordinaire de la Commission mixte - Bruxelles, 19-21 Avril 2016 - PROCES VERBAL)</i> MATIS
2. Data summary	Minutes from joint committee meeting for the Senegalese SFPA in 2016
3. FAIR Data	
3.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata	The minutes are in pdf format and have been provided to FarFish by DG MARE with the conditions that they will not be made publicly available. The minutes are therefore stored in a password protected internal webpage of www.farfish.eu where only selected researchers are granted access.
3.2 Making data openly accessible	The data will not be made openly accessible
3.3 Making data interoperable	No efforts will be made to make the data interoperable. If necessary the minutes might be translated from French to English.
3.4 Increase data re-use (through clarifying licences)	The minutes are only intended for internal use in FarFish.
4. Allocation of resources	No additional cost required.
5. Data security	Data security provided by the technical support of FarFish website.
6. Ethical aspects	No ethical aspects.
7. Other	NA

1. Data set reference/name	<i>Minutes from joint committee meeting for the Senegalese SFPA, held in Dakkar 10-12 April 2017.</i> <i>(ACCORD DE PARTENARIAT DANS LE DOMAINE DE LA PECHE DURABLE ENTRE L'UNION EUROPEENNE ET LA REPUBLIQUE DU SENEGAL - 3ieme session ordinaire de la Commission mixte - Dakar, 10-12 Avril 2017 - PROCES VERBAL) MATIS</i>
2. Data summary	Minutes from joint committee meeting for the Senegalese SFPA in 2017
3. FAIR Data	
3.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata	The minutes are in pdf format and have been provided to FarFish by DG MARE with the conditions that they will not be made publicly available. The minutes are therefore stored in a password protected internal webpage of www.farfish.eu where only selected researchers are granted access.
3.2 Making data openly accessible	The data will not be made openly accessible
3.3 Making data interoperable	No efforts will be made to make the data interoperable. If necessary the minutes might be translated from French to English.
3.4 Increase data re-use (through clarifying licences)	The minutes are only intended for internal use in FarFish.
4. Allocation of resources	No additional cost required.
5. Data security	Data security provided by the technical support of FarFish website.
6. Ethical aspects	No ethical aspects.
7. Other	NA

1. Data set reference/name	<i>Report of the joint committee for the Senegalese SFPA 2018.</i> <i>(Rapport de la réunion annuelle du Comité Scientifique Conjoint relatif à l'Accord de pêche signé entre la République du Sénégal et l'Union européenne - Dakar, 11-13 juillet 2018 -)</i> MATIS
2. Data summary	Report of the joint committee for the Senegalese SFPA 2018.
3. FAIR Data	
3.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata	The report is in pdf format and has been provided to FarFish by DG MARE with the conditions that they will not be made publicly available. The report is therefore stored in a password protected internal webpage of www.farfish.eu where only selected researchers are granted access.
3.2 Making data openly accessible	The data will not be made openly accessible
3.3 Making data interoperable	No efforts will be made to make the data interoperable. If necessary the report might be translated from French to English.
3.4 Increase data re-use (through clarifying licences)	The report is only intended for internal use in FarFish.
4. Allocation of resources	No additional cost required.
5. Data security	Data security provided by the technical support of FarFish website.
6. Ethical aspects	No ethical aspects.
7. Other	NA

1. Data set reference/name	<i>Report of the joint committee for the Senegalese SFPA 2016. (Rapport de la réunion annuelle du Comité Scientifique Conjoint relatif à l'Accord de pêche signé entre la République du Sénégal et l'Union européenne – Dakar, 29 février- 01 & 02 mars 2016)</i> MATIS
2. Data summary	Report of the joint committee for the Senegalese SFPA 2016.
3. FAIR Data	
3.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata	The report is in pdf format and has been provided to FarFish by DG MARE with the conditions that they will not be made publicly available. The report is therefore stored in a password protected internal webpage of www.farfish.eu where only selected researchers are granted access.
3.2 Making data openly accessible	The data will not be made openly accessible
3.3 Making data interoperable	No efforts will be made to make the data interoperable. If necessary the report might be translated from French to English.
3.4 Increase data re-use (through clarifying licences)	The report is only intended for internal use in FarFish.
4. Allocation of resources	No additional cost required.
5. Data security	Data security provided by the technical support of FarFish website.
6. Ethical aspects	No ethical aspects.
7. Other	NA

1. Data set reference/name	<i>Report of the joint committee for the Senegalese SFPA 2017.</i> <i>(Rapport de la réunion annuelle du Comité Scientifique Conjoint relatif à l'Accord de pêche signé entre la République du Sénégal et l'Union européenne – Madrid , 09-11 octobre 2017).</i> MATIS
2. Data summary	Report of the joint committee for the Senegalese SFPA 2017.
3. FAIR Data	
3.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata	The report is in pdf format and has been provided to FarFish by DG MARE with the conditions that they will not be made publicly available. The report is therefore stored in a password protected internal webpage of www.farfish.eu where only selected researchers are granted access.
3.2 Making data openly accessible	The data will not be made openly accessible
3.3 Making data interoperable	No efforts will be made to make the data interoperable. If necessary the report might be translated from French to English.
3.4 Increase data re-use (through clarifying licences)	The report is only intended for internal use in FarFish.
4. Allocation of resources	No additional cost required.
5. Data security	Data security provided by the technical support of FarFish website.
6. Ethical aspects	No ethical aspects.
7. Other	NA

7.1.3 Mauritania

1. Data set reference/name	<i>Minutes from joint committee meeting for the Mauritanian SFPa, held in Brussels 30-31 May 2016</i> <i>(ACCORD DE PARTENARIAT DANS LE SECTEUR DE LA PECHE ENTRE LA REPUBLIQUE ISLAMIQUE DE MAURITANIE ET L'UNION EUROPEENNE - PROTOCOLE 2015-2019 - Procès-verbal de la Commission mixte - Tenue à Bruxelles les 30-31 mai 2016)</i> MATIS
2. Data summary	Minutes from joint committee meeting for the Mauritanian SFPa in 2016
3. FAIR Data	
3.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata	The minutes are in pdf format and have been provided to FarFish by DG MARE with the conditions that they will not be made publicly available. The minutes are therefore stored in a password protected internal webpage of www.farfish.eu where only selected researchers are granted access.
3.2 Making data openly accessible	The data will not be made openly accessible
3.3 Making data interoperable	No efforts will be made to make the data interoperable. If necessary the minutes might be translated from French to English.
3.4 Increase data re-use (through clarifying licences)	The minutes are only intended for internal use in FarFish.
4. Allocation of resources	No additional cost required.
5. Data security	Data security provided by the technical support of FarFish website.
6. Ethical aspects	No ethical aspects.
7. Other	NA

1. Data set reference/name	<i>Minutes from joint committee meeting for the Mauritanian SFPa, held in Brussels 20-22 September 2017.</i> <i>(ACCORD DE PARTENARIAT DANS LE SECTEUR DE LA PECHE ENTRE LA REPUBLIQUE ISLAMIQUE DE MAURITANIE ET L'UNION EUROPEENNE - PROTOCOLE 2015-2019 - Procès-verbal de la Commission mixte - Tenue à Bruxelles les 20, 21 et 22 septembre 2017)</i> MATIS
2. Data summary	Minutes from joint committee meeting for the Mauritanian SFPa in 2017
3. FAIR Data	
3.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata	The minutes are in pdf format and have been provided to FarFish by DG MARE with the conditions that they will not be made publicly available. The minutes are therefore stored in a password protected internal webpage of www.farfish.eu where only selected researchers are granted access.
3.2 Making data openly accessible	The data will not be made openly accessible
3.3 Making data interoperable	No efforts will be made to make the data interoperable. If necessary the minutes might be translated from French to English.
3.4 Increase data re-use (through clarifying licences)	The minutes are only intended for internal use in FarFish.
4. Allocation of resources	No additional cost required.
5. Data security	Data security provided by the technical support of FarFish website.
6. Ethical aspects	No ethical aspects.
7. Other	NA

1. Data set reference/name	<i>Report of the joint committee for the Mauritanian SFPA, for the period 2008-2012; 2013-2014 and 2015-2019. Report published in September 2017. (Rapport conjoint d'exécution et de programmation des Appuis sectoriels 2008-2012; 2013-2014 et 2015-2019)</i> MATIS
2. Data summary	Report of the joint committee for the Mauritanian SFPA, for the period 2008-2012; 2013-2014 and 2015-2019
3. FAIR Data	
3.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata	The report is in pdf format and has been provided to FarFish by DG MARE with the conditions that they will not be made publicly available. The report is therefore stored in a password protected internal webpage of www.farfish.eu where only selected researchers are granted access.
3.2 Making data openly accessible	The data will not be made openly accessible
3.3 Making data interoperable	No efforts will be made to make the data interoperable. If necessary the report might be translated from French to English.
3.4 Increase data re-use (through clarifying licences)	The report is only intended for internal use in FarFish.
4. Allocation of resources	No additional cost required.
5. Data security	Data security provided by the technical support of FarFish website.
6. Ethical aspects	No ethical aspects.
7. Other	NA

1. Data set reference/name	<i>Report of the joint committee for the Mauritanian SFPA 2016.</i> <i>(Rapport de la Réunion annuelle du Comité Scientifique Conjointe relatif à l'Accord de pêche signé entre la République islamique de Mauritanie et l'Union européenne - – Nouakchott, 05 au 07 septembre 2016)</i> MATIS
2. Data summary	Report of the joint committee for the Mauritanian SFPA 2016.
3. FAIR Data	
3.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata	The report is in pdf format and has been provided to FarFish by DG MARE with the conditions that they will not be made publicly available. The report is therefore stored in a password protected internal webpage of www.farfish.eu where only selected researchers are granted access.
3.2 Making data openly accessible	The data will not be made openly accessible
3.3 Making data interoperable	No efforts will be made to make the data interoperable. If necessary the report might be translated from French to English.
3.4 Increase data re-use (through clarifying licences)	The report is only intended for internal use in FarFish.
4. Allocation of resources	No additional cost required.
5. Data security	Data security provided by the technical support of FarFish website.
6. Ethical aspects	No ethical aspects.
7. Other	NA

1. Data set reference/name	<i>Minutes from joint committee meeting for the Mauritanian SFPA, held in Nouakchott 15-16 November 2016.</i> <i>(ACCORD DE PARTENARIAT DANS LE SECTEUR DE LA PECHE ENTRE LA REPUBLIQUE ISLAMIQUE DE MAURITANIE ET L'UNION EUROPEENNE - PROTOCOLE 2015-2019 - Procès-verbal de la Commission mixte extraordinaire - Tenue à Nouakchott les 15-16 novembre 2016)</i> MATIS
2. Data summary	Minutes from joint committee meeting for the Mauritanian SFPA in 2016
3. FAIR Data	
3.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata	The minutes are in pdf format and have been provided to FarFish by DG MARE with the conditions that they will not be made publicly available. The minutes are therefore stored in a password protected internal webpage of www.farfish.eu where only selected researchers are granted access.
3.2 Making data openly accessible	The data will not be made openly accessible
3.3 Making data interoperable	No efforts will be made to make the data interoperable. If necessary the minutes might be translated from French to English.
3.4 Increase data re-use (through clarifying licences)	The minutes are only intended for internal use in FarFish.
4. Allocation of resources	No additional cost required.
5. Data security	Data security provided by the technical support of FarFish website.
6. Ethical aspects	No ethical aspects.
7. Other	NA

1. Data set reference/name	<i>Report of the joint committee for the Mauritanian SFPA 2017. (Rapport de la Réunion annuelle du Comité Scientifique Conjoint relatif à l'Accord de pêche signé entre la République islamique de Mauritanie et l'Union européenne Santa Cruz de Tenerife - 03 au 05 octobre 2017 -)</i> MATIS
2. Data summary	Report of the joint committee for the Mauritanian SFPA 2017.
3. FAIR Data	
3.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata	The report is in pdf format and has been provided to FarFish by DG MARE with the conditions that they will not be made publicly available. The report is therefore stored in a password protected internal webpage of www.farfish.eu where only selected researchers are granted access.
3.2 Making data openly accessible	The data will not be made openly accessible
3.3 Making data interoperable	No efforts will be made to make the data interoperable. If necessary the report might be translated from French to English.
3.4 Increase data re-use (through clarifying licences)	The report is only intended for internal use in FarFish.
4. Allocation of resources	No additional cost required.
5. Data security	Data security provided by the technical support of FarFish website.
6. Ethical aspects	No ethical aspects.
7. Other	NA

1. Data set reference/name	<i>Dataset for small pelagics value chain in Mauritania</i> UoP
2. Data summary	Datasets for the study of the value chain of small pelagic in Mauritania. Includes data on reported landings and catches, trade flow, imports and exports.
3. FAIR Data	
3.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata	The dataset is in excel format and it is openly accessible in the FarFish repository in Zenodo. https://zenodo.org/record/5702666#.YZOCc0bP3OQ
3.2 Making data openly accessible	Data is available online in a searchable database in the FarFish repository in Zenodo. https://zenodo.org/record/5702666#.YZOCc0bP3OQ
3.3 Making data interoperable	All data produced for the project were delivered and circulated among partners and stakeholders according to the project's guidelines
3.4 Increase data re-use (through clarifying licences)	All data collections, also fully-documented, are organized by records, Fact Sheets and graphs, thus complementing the overall statistical collections
4. Allocation of resources	NA
5. Data security	Security of original databases is operated by Zenodo. Collections and data produced for the project will be stored in the data server belonging to University of Portsmouth. The data produced for the project FarFish will be stored for a period of 10 years after project's completion.
6. Ethical aspects	All copyrights and authorship will be attributed according to academic rigor and integrity
7. Other	NA

7.1.4 Cabo Verde

1. Data set reference/name	<i>Minutes from joint committee meeting for the Cabo Verde SFPA, held in Brussels 12 October 2018. (Accord de Partenariat de Peche Durable entre l'Union Européenne et Cabo Verde PROTOCOLE 2014-2018 COMMISSION MIXTE - BRUXELLES, 12 OCTOBRE 2018) MATIS</i>
2. Data summary	Minutes from joint committee meeting for the Cabo Verde SFPA in 2018
3. FAIR Data	
3.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata	The minutes are in pdf format and have been provided to FarFish by DG MARE with the conditions that they will not be made publicly available. The minutes are therefore stored in a password protected internal webpage of www.farfish.eu where only selected researchers are granted access.
3.2 Making data openly accessible	The data will not be made openly accessible
3.3 Making data interoperable	No efforts will be made to make the data interoperable. If necessary the minutes might be translated from French to English.
3.4 Increase data re-use (through clarifying licences)	The minutes are only intended for internal use in FarFish.
4. Allocation of resources	No additional cost required.
5. Data security	Data security provided by the technical support of FarFish website.
6. Ethical aspects	No ethical aspects.
7. Other	NA

1. Data set reference/name	<i>Minutes from joint committee meeting for the Cabo Verde SFPA, held in Brussels 23-25 March 2015.</i> <i>(ACCORD DE PARTENARIAT DANS LE SECTEUR DE LA PECHE ENTRE L'UNION EUROPEENNE ET LA REPUBLIQUE DU CAP VERT PROTOCOLE 2014-2018 COMMISSION MIXTE - BRUXELLES, 23-25 MARS 2015 - PROCES VERBAL) MATIS</i>
2. Data summary	Minutes from joint committee meeting for the Cabo Verde SFPA in 2015.
3. FAIR Data	
3.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata	The minutes are in pdf format and have been provided to FarFish by DG MARE with the conditions that they will not be made publicly available. The minutes are therefore stored in a password protected internal webpage of www.farfish.eu where only selected researchers are granted access.
3.2 Making data openly accessible	The data will not be made openly accessible
3.3 Making data interoperable	No efforts will be made to make the data interoperable. If necessary the minutes might be translated from French to English.
3.4 Increase data re-use (through clarifying licences)	The minutes are only intended for internal use in FarFish.
4. Allocation of resources	No additional cost required.
5. Data security	Data security provided by the technical support of FarFish website.
6. Ethical aspects	No ethical aspects.
7. Other	NA

1. Data set reference/name	<i>Minutes from joint committee meeting for the Cabo Verde SFPAs, held in Brussels 28-29 November 2017.</i> <i>(Accord de Partenariat de Peche Durable NTRE L'UNION EUROPEENNE ET LE CABO VERDE</i> <i>PROTOCOLE 2014-2018 COMMISSION MIXTE - BRUXELLES, 28-29 NOVEMBRE 2017- PROCES VERBAL)</i> MATIS
2. Data summary	Minutes from joint committee meeting for the Cabo Verde SFPAs in 2017.
3. FAIR Data	
3.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata	The minutes are in pdf format and have been provided to FarFish by DG MARE with the conditions that they will not be made publicly available. The minutes are therefore stored in a password protected internal webpage of www.farfish.eu where only selected researchers are granted access.
3.2 Making data openly accessible	The data will not be made openly accessible
3.3 Making data interoperable	No efforts will be made to make the data interoperable. If necessary the minutes might be translated from French to English.
3.4 Increase data re-use (through clarifying licences)	The minutes are only intended for internal use in FarFish.
4. Allocation of resources	No additional cost required.
5. Data security	Data security provided by the technical support of FarFish website.
6. Ethical aspects	No ethical aspects.
7. Other	NA

1. Data set reference/name	<i>Minutes from joint committee meeting for the Cabo Verde SFPa, held in Mindelo 11-13 May 2016.</i> <i>(ACCORD DE PARTENARIAT DANS LE SECTEUR DE LA PECHE ENTRE L'UNION EUROPEENNE ET LA REPUBLIQUE DU CABO VERDE PROTOCOLE 2014-2018 COMMISSION MIXTE - MINDELO, 11-13 MAI 2016- PROCES VERBAL)</i> MATIS
2. Data summary	Minutes from joint committee meeting for the Cabo Verde SFPa in 2016.
3. FAIR Data	
3.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata	The minutes are in pdf format and have been provided to FarFish by DG MARE with the conditions that they will not be made publicly available. The minutes are therefore stored in a password protected internal webpage of www.farfish.eu where only selected researchers are granted access.
3.2 Making data openly accessible	The data will not be made openly accessible
3.3 Making data interoperable	No efforts will be made to make the data interoperable. If necessary the minutes might be translated from French to English.
3.4 Increase data re-use (through clarifying licences)	The minutes are only intended for internal use in FarFish.
4. Allocation of resources	No additional cost required.
5. Data security	Data security provided by the technical support of FarFish website.
6. Ethical aspects	No ethical aspects.
7. Other	NA

1. Data set reference/name	<i>Dataset tuna value chains from the West African SFPAs</i> UoP
2. Data summary	The dataset includes catches of tuna from the pole and longliners, purse seiners per country of origin. Raw data source DG-Mare, not available online. Countries analysed: Angola, Côte d'Ivoire, Cabo Verde, Gabon, Ghana, Guinea, Guinea Bissau, Liberia, Mauritania, Senegal, Sierra Leone, Sao Tome y Principe. Years analysed: 2014 - 2019
3. FAIR Data	
3.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata	The dataset is in excel format and it is openly accessible in the FarFish repository in Zenodo. https://zenodo.org/record/5702645#.YZOEmEbP3OQ
3.2 Making data openly accessible	Data is available online in a searchable database in the FarFish repository in Zenodo. https://zenodo.org/record/5702645#.YZOEmEbP3OQ
3.3 Making data interoperable	All data produced for the project were delivered and circulated among partners and stakeholders according to the project's guidelines
3.4 Increase data re-use (through clarifying licences)	All data collections, also fully-documented, are organized by records, Fact Sheets and graphs, thus complementing the overall statistical collections
4. Allocation of resources	NA
5. Data security	Security of original databases is operated by Zenodo. Collections and data produced for the project will be stored in the data server belonging to University of Portsmouth. The data produced for the project FarFish will be stored for a period of 10 years after project's completion.
6. Ethical aspects	All copyrights and authorship will be attributed according to academic rigor and integrity
7. Other	NA

7.1.6 South-East Atlantic

1. Data set reference/name	<i>REPORT OF THE 12th SEAFO SCIENTIFIC COMMITTEE</i> IMR
2. Data summary	Report of the 12 th SEAFO Scientific Committee. The report contains meeting agenda/minutes from the 12 th SEAFO Scientific Committee Meeting, as well as tables/reports on catch, stock status, landings, discard and bycatch.
3. FAIR Data	
3.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata	The report can be downloaded directly from the link: http://www.seafo.org/media/4ca98f5f-c111-4bcf-875b-36ac3213b8b7/SEAFOweb/pdf/SC/open/eng/SC%20Report%202016_pdf . Other reports can be accessed at the SEAFO web site: http://www.seafo.org/Documents .
3.2 Making data openly accessible	The data is openly accessible.
3.3 Making data interoperable	The report on the 12 th SEAFO Scientific Committee is available in PDF-format, as are other reports which can be access from the SEAFO website http://www.seafo.org/Documents . All reports are available in English.
3.4 Increase data re-use (through clarifying licences)	NA
4. Allocation of resources	Not applicable.
5. Data security	Data reside on a secure server and is backed-up on a regularly basis.
6. Ethical aspects	Not applicable.
7. Other	NA

1. Data set reference/name	<i>REPORT OF THE 12th SEAFO SCIENTIFIC COMMITTEE</i> IMR
2. Data summary	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The dataset contains information on all data gathered for management and policy decision making purposes, for scientific analysis and to meet obligations to international bodies. Data is collected from Fishing vessels (logbook) and is captured, processed and managed by the SEAFO.
3. FAIR Data	
3.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata	A PDF report based on the data is available for download at http://www.seafo.org/media/4ca98f5f-c111-4bcf-875b-36ac3213b8b7/SEAFOweb/pdf/SC/open/eng/SC%20Report%202016_pdf
3.2 Making data openly accessible	The data is openly accessible.
3.3 Making data interoperable	The report on the 12 th SEAFO Scientific Committee is available in PDF-format, as are other reports which can be access from the SEAFO website http://www.seafo.org/Documents . All reports are available in English.
3.4 Increase data re-use (through clarifying licences)	Published data will be re-usable
4. Allocation of resources	Not applicable.
5. Data security	Data reside on a secure server and is backed-up on a regularly basis.
6. Ethical aspects	Not applicable.
7. Other	NA

7.1.7 South-West Atlantic

1. Data set reference/name	<i>Catches of three main species in the Southwest Atlantic area FAO 41 from FAO - FAO. 2020. Fishery and Aquaculture Statistics. Global capture production 1950-2018 (FishstatJ). In: FAO Fisheries and Aquaculture Department [online]. Rome. Updated 2020.</i> Sjókovin
2. Data summary	The dataset includes report on catches from the three main species (Argentine hake, Argentine shortfin squid, Argentine red shrimp) in the Southwest Atlantic area FAO 41. Raw data is extracted from FAO Capture, Aquaculture and Global production databases have been updated with an additional year and now include data from 1950 to 2018.
3. FAIR Data	
3.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata	Database in the FarFish repository in Zenodo. https://zenodo.org/record/5603362#.YXqZ_dbML0o FAO ensures quality assurance by documenting each collection to highlight definitions and to specify the structure, sources, coverage, processes, intended use, etc. This is complemented with the <i>CWP Handbook of Fishery Statistical Standards</i> which includes comprehensive definitions of concepts and details of standard classifications. Available at: http://www.fao.org/fishery/cwp/search/en
3.2 Making data openly accessible	Data is available online in a searchable database in the FarFish repository in Zenodo.
3.3 Making data interoperable	All data produced for the project were delivered and circulated among partners and stakeholders according to the project's guidelines.
3.4 Increase data re-use (through clarifying licences)	All data collections, also fully-documented, are organized by records, Fact Sheets and graphs, thus complementing the overall statistical collections
4. Allocation of resources	NA
5. Data security	Security of original databases is operated by FAO. Security of the specific dataset is operated by Zenodo. Collections and data produced for the project will be storage in the data server belonging to Sjókovin. The data produced for the project FarFish will be stored for a period of 10 years after project's completion.
6. Ethical aspects	All copyrights and authorship will be attributed according to academic rigor and integrity
7. Other	NA

1. Data set reference/name	<i>Trade data hake Southwest Atlantic</i> Sjókovin
2. Data summary	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Trade statistics of Argentine hake from main actors in the Southwest Atlantic fisheries (Argentina, Spain and Falkland/Malvinas Islands) • Trade statistics are derived from official national and international sources including ITC, UN COMTRADE, National Institute of Statistics and Census - Republic of Argentina and Fisheries Department from Falkland/Malvinas Islands
3. FAIR Data	
3.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata	<p>Database in the FarFish repository in Zenodo. Metadata is available at:</p> <p>https://www.trademap.org/Index.aspx https://www.indec.gob.ar/indec/web/Nivel4-Tema-3-2-39 https://comtrade.un.org/pb/ https://www.fig.gov.fk/fisheries/publications/fishery-statistics?task=download.send&id=210&catid=7&m=0</p>
3.2 Making data openly accessible	Data is available online in a searchable database in the FarFish repository in Zenodo. https://zenodo.org/record/5616246#.YXvpjkbMLOQ
3.3 Making data interoperable	All data produced for the project were delivered and circulated among partners and stakeholders according to the project's guidelines
3.4 Increase data re-use (through clarifying licences)	All data collections, also fully-documented, are organized by records, Fact Sheets and graphs, thus complementing the overall statistical collections
4. Allocation of resources	NA
5. Data security	<p>Security of original databases is operated by ITC, UN, INDEC and FIG. Security of the specific dataset is operated by Zenodo.</p> <p>Collections and data produced for the project will be storage in the data server belonging to Sjókovin.</p> <p>The data produced for the project FarFish will be stored for a period of 10 years after project's completion.</p>
6. Ethical aspects	All copyrights and authorship will be attributed according to academic rigor and integrity
7. Other	NA

1. Data set reference/name	<i>Catches of Argentine hake patagonian stock in the Southwest Atlantic</i> Sjókovin
2. Data summary	The dataset includes catches of Argentine hake from the patagonian stock specifically, in the EEZ of Argentina and in the waters around the Falkland Islands under UK control. Data from 1987 to 2020 in thousand tonnes
3. FAIR Data	
3.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata	Database in the FarFish repository in Zenodo Metadata is available at: https://www.fig.gov.fk/fisheries/publications/finfish?task=download.send&id=206&catid=10&m=0
3.2 Making data openly accessible	Data is available online in a searchable database in the FarFish repository in Zenodo. https://zenodo.org/record/5616472#.YXvpYUbMLOQ
3.3 Making data interoperable	All data produced for the project were delivered and circulated among partners and stakeholders according to the project's guidelines
3.4 Increase data re-use (through clarifying licences)	All data collections, also fully-documented, are organized by records, Fact Sheets and graphs, thus complementing the overall statistical collections
4. Allocation of resources	NA
5. Data security	Security of original databases is operated FIG. Security of the specific dataset is operated by Zenodo. Collections and data produced for the project will be storage in the data server belonging to Sjókovin. The data produced for the project FarFish will be stored for a period of 10 years after project's completion.
6. Ethical aspects	All copyrights and authorship will be attributed according to academic rigor and integrity
7. Other	NA

7.1.8 Morocco

1. Data set reference/name	<i>Dataset for small pelagic stocks assessment in Moroccan Atlantic coast</i> UCA
2. Data summary	Datasets for stock assessment of small pelagic stocks in Moroccan Atlantic coast, Including available data on catches (all small pelagic stocks), fishing effort (sardine and chub mackerel stocks), age and length composition of landings (sardine and chub mackerel stocks), biological parameters (sardine, chub mackerel and anchovy), surveys data (sardine, chub mackerel and anchovy).
3. FAIR Data	
3.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata	The dataset is in excel format and it is openly accessible in the FarFish repository in Zenodo. https://zenodo.org/record/6371237-.YjcochDMKdY
3.2 Making data openly accessible	Data is available online and can be downloaded at : https://zenodo.org/record/6371237-.YjcochDMKdY
3.3 Making data interoperable	Data are interoperable.
3.4 Increase data re-use (through clarifying licences)	The data is publicly available for all. No login required.
4. Allocation of resources	NA
5. Data security	Security of original databases is operated by Zenodo.
6. Ethical aspects	No known ethical aspects.
7. Other	NA

7.1.9 Non-case study specific

1. Data set reference/name	STECF Economic data for Purse seiners and hook vessels 2015 2018 Nofima
2. Data summary	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Extract from STECF database • Data on technical aspects, costs and earnings, employment • For vessel groups ESP/FRA OFR PS 40XX and ESP OFR HOK 2440 • Covering 2015 to 2018
3. FAIR Data	
3.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata	The data and metadata as available on the FarFish community on Zenodo https://zenodo.org/record/5607123#.YX-5yRrMKUk
3.2 Making data openly accessible	Data is available to the public. Data is available online in a searchable database. No login required. The website and data sets are available in various languages https://stecf.jrc.ec.europa.eu/reports/economic
3.3 Making data interoperable	Extracted data are provided in excel format on Zenodo.
3.4 Increase data re-use (through clarifying licences)	The relevant reports of the STECF where the same data are also published (https://stecf.jrc.ec.europa.eu/data-reports). Documentation on the data variables and their definitions together with a publication date are also provided.
4. Allocation of resources	NA
5. Data security	Security of original databases is operated by STECF and the European Commission
6. Ethical aspects	STECF states that the data are made available in the interests of transparency and can be freely used for further analyses provided the source is acknowledged, according to disclaimer available at: https://stecf.jrc.ec.europa.eu/data-dissemination
7. Other	NA

1. Data set reference/name	<i>Data on EU vessel tuna catches in ICCAT by 5 degree gridcells in 2018</i> Nofima
2. Data summary	Data contains catches of tuna by species from EU vessels in the ICCAT area in 2018 by 5 degree gridcells
3. FAIR Data	
3.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata	The original databases are publicly available and updated on http://www.iccat.int/en/accesingdb.htm . Metadata and code descriptions are provided here: https://www.iccat.int/en/stat_codes.html The dataset used is available on the FarFish community on Zenodo: https://zenodo.org/record/5607100#_YX-5ZhrMKUk
3.2 Making data openly accessible	Data is available online in a searchable database. No login required. The website and data sets are available in English, French and Spanish. http://www.iccat.int/en/accesingdb.htm
3.3 Making data interoperable	Data is provided in excel format. No login required. Additional data clarification is available for Task II data at http://www.iccat.int/Data/t2ce-ENG.pdf
3.4 Increase data re-use (through clarifying licences)	The dissemination of ICCAT data is according to the Rules and Procedures for the protection, access to, and dissemination of data compiled by ICCAT, adopted by the Commission in 2010. Available at http://www.iccat.int/Data/REP_EN_10-11_I_1_Annex_6_Confidentiality.pdf .
4. Allocation of resources	Not yet defined
5. Data security	Security of original databases is operated by ICAAT The extracted data are hosted on Zenondo
6. Ethical aspects	NA
7. Other	NA

1. Data set reference/name	<i>Export quantity of fish meal and fish oil from Mauritania 2010 2020</i> Nofima
2. Data summary	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Export quantities in kg of fish meal and fish oil from Mauritania. • Time period 2010 to 2020 • Data source is UN Comtrade and Trademap.org
3. FAIR Data	
3.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Dataset used is published on Zenodo: https://zenodo.org/record/5607086#.YX-6HxrMKUk. • Variables are self-explanatory
3.2 Making data openly accessible	UN Comtrade data can be extracted from https://comtrade.un.org/data Metadata are provided at the same site. Trademap data are available from trademap.org. Metadata are as for UN comtrade.
3.3 Making data interoperable	The data is interoperable. The products are classified through Harmonized System Codes - HS (2,4 & 6) and SITC.
3.4 Increase data re-use (through clarifying licences)	The data is publicly available for all. No login required.
4. Allocation of resources	No additional costs required.
5. Data security	Original data are hosted by UN Statistics Division and follows their guidelines for data security. The data extract is hosted by Zenodo
6. Ethical aspects	No known ethical aspects.
7. Other	NA

1. Data set reference/name	<i>Tuna_exports_west_africa_2014_2019_FishstatJ</i> Nofima
2. Data summary	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • These data contains export statistics for tuna products for the West-African countries Cabo Verde, Senegal, Ghana and Cote d'Ivoire • Quantity and value information on an annual basis per commodity type classified using the FAO International Standard Statistical Classification of Fishery Commodities, derived from SITC and linked to HS codes with two levels aggregation • Information on trade is collected annually primarily from country reports provided to FAO , but also trade yearbooks, bulletins, questionnaires, and UN comtrade data
3. FAIR Data	
3.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata	Metadata are available at http://www.fao.org/fishery/statistics/global-commodities-production/3/en . Data Periodicity: Data are reported yearly and the period used is the calendar year (1 January - 31 December.) Some countries or areas use a split-year in their reporting (e.g. year ending 30 June.)
3.2 Making data openly accessible	The commodity trade dataset can be downloaded at https://zenodo.org/record/5539861
3.3 Making data interoperable	Data are interoperable.
3.4 Increase data re-use (through clarifying licences)	Data are public. No login required. See FAO guidelines on data reuse.
4. Allocation of resources	No additional costs required.
5. Data security	Data are hosted online by zenondo
6. Ethical aspects	No known ethical aspects.
7. Other	NA

1. Data set reference/name	<i>Tuna_imports_EU_west_africa_2015_2019</i> Nofima
2. Data summary	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Import to EU of tuna products from Cabo Verde, Senegal, Ghana and Cote d'Ivoire. Tuna products are selected based on name and HS-6 codes. • Extracted from Comext dataset "EU trade since 1988 by HS-2-4-6 and CN8" for all EU countries grouped • Quantity in 100 kg and value in Euro • Import to EU Member state per HS-6 code (product ID), reporting and partner country. Only Extra-EU are relevant. The • Extra-EU trade statistics record goods imported and exported by the EU from and to non-EU countries. • Extra-EU data on trade in goods with non-EU countries are collected by customs authorities and are based on the records of trade transactions in customs declarations. Extra-EU trade statistics do not cover goods declared orally to customs authorities which are non-commercial, or which are of a commercial nature but have a value not exceeding the statistical threshold of EUR 1 000 and 1 000 kg.
3. FAIR Data	
3.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Metadata are available from the Easy Comext domain (link).
3.2 Making data openly accessible	The dataset used can be downloaded at: https://zenodo.org/record/5539855
3.3 Making data interoperable	The data is interoperable. The products are classified through Harmonized System Codes - HS 6
3.4 Increase data re-use (through clarifying licences)	The data is publicly available for all. No login required. Provisions regarding data reuse is specified through Eurostat guidelines (http://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/about/policies/copyright).
4. Allocation of resources	No additional costs required.
5. Data security	Data are hosted by zenodo
6. Ethical aspects	No known ethical aspects. See Commissions regulations for data confidentiality http://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/web/research-methodology/statistical-confidentiality .
7. Other	NA

1. Data set reference/name	<i>DG MARE – SFPAs Evaluation reports</i> Nofima
2. Data summary	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The ex-post/ex-ante evaluation reports of the SFPAs agreements contains a review of the country background, fisheries sector (important fisheries, economic figures, employment, governing bodies), whether the agreements are suited to achieve the goals set, and recommendations for future protocols. The reports are based on information gathered from various sources (e.g. EU departments and executive agencies, EU-member states administrative bodies, professional association groupings, regional associations, etc).
3. FAIR Data	
3.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata	Reports are in PDF-format and are available in a searchable database: https://ec.europa.eu/fisheries/documentation/studies .
3.2 Making data openly accessible	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The reports are openly accessible and available to the public in a searchable database. No login is required, nor are there any regional lockout mechanisms. The website is available in all EU-partners' languages. The reports are available in either English or French. For reports in French only, an English summary is presented.
3.3 Making data interoperable	All data collected during the course of farFish were distributed among partners and stakeholders according to FarFish guidelines.
3.4 Increase data re-use (through clarifying licences)	Re-use of content is authorised provided the source is acknowledged, and follows the Commissions reuse policy as defined in " <i>Commission Decision of 12 December 2011 on the reuse of Commission documents</i> " http://eur-lex.europa.eu/LexUriServ/LexUriServ.do?uri=OJ:L:2011:330:0039:0042:EN:PDF (available in English).
4. Allocation of resources	No additional costs required.
5. Data security	Reports are available on an EU-hosted website, and follows EUs guidelines for data security.
6. Ethical aspects	No known ethical aspects.
7. Other	NA

1. Data set reference/name	<i>Model outputs an indicators – Data summary, estimates and projections</i> CSIC
2. Data summary	Data provided by model outputs could be a summary of the data available, reference points, indicators (as the estimated TAC value), biomass estimates or forward projections.
3. FAIR Data	
3.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata	Relevant datasets are uploaded to the FFDB and to Zenodo with keywords referring to the species, location and type of the data (could be a summary of the data available, reference points, biomass estimates or forward projections).
3.2 Making data openly accessible	Data sets, e.g. spreadsheets files, will be published on the website https://www.farfish.eu as part of the data management plan (DMP) and on Zenodo.
3.3 Making data interoperable	Project-generated data are shared in the web https://www.farfish.eu and on Zenodo https://zenodo.org/record/5541269 The Data base allows transformation into txt. xls and csv files to favour an easy interaction.
3.4 Increase data re-use (through clarifying licences)	Data were uploaded on the Farfish website and Zenodo. Data are stored for an indefinite time.
4. Allocation of resources	No additional cost required.
5. Data security	Data security provided by the technical support of Farfish website and Zenodo.
6. Ethical aspects	No known ethical aspects yet.
7. Other	NA

1. Data set reference/name	<i>Historical Fisheries data – Catches/survey time series</i> CSIC
2. Data summary	Historical fisheries data could be catches time series or survey time series. The data could be obtained from international databases and research centers as well as from scientific publications.
3. FAIR Data	
3.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata	Relevant datasets are uploaded to the FFDB and Zenodo, with keywords referring to the species, location and type of the data (could be mainly catches time series or surveys time series).
3.2 Making data openly accessible	Data sets, e.g. spreadsheets files, will be published on the website https://www.farfish.eu and Zenodo https://zenodo.org/record/5541279 as part of the data management plan (DMP).
3.3 Making data interoperable	Project-generated data are shared in the website (if possible) and in designated scientific publications. The Database allows transformation into txt. xls and csv files to favour an easy interaction.
3.4 Increase data re-use (through clarifying licences)	Data were uploaded on the Farfish website (with password provided to Farfish members if the data set has some legal conflict) and on Zenodo. Data are stored for an indefinite time.
4. Allocation of resources	No additional cost required.
5. Data security	Data security provided by the technical support of Farfish website and Zenodo.
6. Ethical aspects	No known ethical aspects yet.
7. Other	NA

1. Data set reference/name	<i>Biological fisheries data – Maturity, growth, mortality</i> CSIC
2. Data summary	Data regarding biological aspects of the fisheries can include maturity, growth, mortality and life cycle relevant aspects. The data can be obtained from: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - International Databases - Marine research institutes - Oceanographic research centers
3. FAIR Data	
3.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata	Relevant datasets are uploaded to the FFDB and on Zenodo, with keywords referring to the species, location and type of the data (could be maturity, growth, mortality and life cycle relevant aspects).
3.2 Making data openly accessible	The described sources utilize the standard nomenclature for statistical data. Data sets, e.g. spreadsheets files, will be published on the website https://www.farfish.eu and on Zenodo https://zenodo.org/record/5541281 as part of the data management plan (DMP).
3.3 Making data interoperable	Project-generated data are shared in the website (if possible) and in designated scientific publications. The Database allows transformation into txt. xls and csv files to favour an easy interaction.
3.4 Increase data re-use (through clarifying licences)	Data were uploaded on the Farfish website (with password provided to Farfish members if the data set has some legal conflict) and on Zenodo. Data are stored for an indefinite time.
4. Allocation of resources	No additional cost required.
5. Data security	Data security provided by the technical support of Farfish website and Zenodo.
6. Ethical aspects	No known ethical aspects yet.
7. Other	NA

1. Data set reference/name	<i>Decision Support and visualisation tools outputs</i> CSIC
2. Data summary	Summary of the meetings conclusions, surveys results, preference measures given by stakeholders on different options or a summary of model inputs and outputs.
3. FAIR Data	
3.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata	Relevant datasets are uploaded to the FFDB and on Zenodo with keywords referring to the species, location, type of the data and type of DST used.
3.2 Making data openly accessible	Data sets, e.g. spreadsheets files, will be published on the website https://www.farfish.eu and on Zenodo https://zenodo.org/record/5541290 as part of the data management plan (DMP).
3.3 Making data interoperable	Project-generated data are shared in the FarFish website and on Zenodo The Data base allows transformation into txt. xls and csv files to favour an easy interaction.
3.4 Increase data re-use (through clarifying licences)	Data were uploaded on the Farfish website and on Zenodo. Data are stored for an indefinite time.
4. Allocation of resources	No additional cost required.
5. Data security	Data security provided by the technical support of Farfish website and Zenodo.
6. Ethical aspects	No known ethical aspects yet.
7. Other	NA

1. Data set reference/name	<i>Environmental (hydrodynamic) conditions on the NW African coast from 3D reanalysis models</i> WP6 CSIC
2. Data summary	This dataset contain hydrodynamic and biogeochemical variables extracted from the CMEMS service (https://marine.copernicus.eu/) covering the NW region of the African coast and the period 1993 to 2019. The environmental dataset include: water temperature, water salinity, u-velocity and v-velocity.
3. FAIR Data	
3.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata	Data are available on Zenodo under the FarFish community : https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6378537
3.2 Making data openly accessible	Data are available on Zenodo under the FarFish community : https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6378537
3.3 Making data interoperable	File opens with matlab
3.4 Increase data re-use (through clarifying licences)	Data are available on Zenodo under the FarFish community : https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6378537
4. Allocation of resources	NA
5. Data security	Data security follows the guideline of Zenodo
6. Ethical aspects	NA
7. Other	NA

1. Data set reference/name	<i>Environmental (biogeochemical) conditions on the NW African coast from 3D reanalysis models</i> WP6 CSIC
2. Data summary	This dataset contain hydrodynamic and biogeochemical variables extracted from the CMEMS service (https://marine.copernicus.eu/) covering the NW region of the African coast and the period 1993 to 2019. The environmental dataset include: nitrate concentration, phosphate concentration and chlorophyll-a concentration.
3. FAIR Data	
3.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata	Data are available on Zenodo under the FarFish community : https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6378807
3.2 Making data openly accessible	Data are available on Zenodo under the FarFish community : https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6378807
3.3 Making data interoperable	File opens with matlab
3.4 Increase data re-use (through clarifying licences)	Data are available on Zenodo under the FarFish community : https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6378807
4. Allocation of resources	NA
5. Data security	Data security follows the guideline of Zenodo
6. Ethical aspects	NA
7. Other	NA

1. Data set reference/name	<i>Environmental (oxygen) conditions on the NW African coast from 3D reanalysis models</i> WP6 CSIC
2. Data summary	This dataset contain hydrodynamic and biogeochemical variables extracted from the CMEMS service (https://marine.copernicus.eu/) covering the NW region of the African coast and the period 1993 to 2019. The environmental dataset include subsurface (100 to 200m) oxygen concentration.
3. FAIR Data	
3.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata	Data are available on Zenodo under the FarFish community : https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6378818
3.2 Making data openly accessible	Data are available on Zenodo under the FarFish community : https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6378818
3.3 Making data interoperable	File opens with matlab
3.4 Increase data re-use (through clarifying licences)	Data are available on Zenodo under the FarFish community : https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6378818
4. Allocation of resources	NA
5. Data security	Data security follows the guideline of Zenodo
6. Ethical aspects	NA
7. Other	NA

1. Data set reference/name	<i>Catch reports by EU vessels in the SFPA of Seychelles, Mauritania, Cabo Verde and Senegal in 2014-2019</i> MATIS
2. Data summary	Catch reports in pdf from an excel sheet.
3. FAIR Data	
3.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata	The data is in pdf format and has been provided to FarFish by DG MARE with the conditions that they will not be made publicly available. The report is therefore stored in a password protected internal webpage of www.farfish.eu where only selected researchers are granted access.
3.2 Making data openly accessible	The data will not be made openly accessible
3.3 Making data interoperable	No efforts will be made to make the data interoperable.
3.4 Increase data re-use (through clarifying licences)	The report is only intended for internal use in FarFish.
4. Allocation of resources	No additional cost required.
5. Data security	Data security provided by the technical support of FarFish website.
6. Ethical aspects	No ethical aspects.
7. Other	NA

1. Data set reference/name	<i>Catch reports by EU vessels in non-EU waters in 2014-2019</i> MATIS
2. Data summary	Excel sheet containing detailed catch and landing reports that show by fishing vessel, species and fishing trip information on MS registration of vessel, registration nr. of vessel, month of fishing trip, fishing area, fishing gear, specie, landing information (including utilisation e.g. fishmeal, non-human, Discard, human consumption...) and weight
3. FAIR Data	
3.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata	The data is in an excel file provided to FarFish by DG MARE with the conditions that they will not be made publicly available as a whole, but aggregated data can be made available. The report is therefore stored in a password protected internal webpage of www.farfish.eu where only selected researchers are granted access.
3.2 Making data openly accessible	The data as a whole will not be made openly accessible.
3.3 Making data interoperable	No efforts will be made to make the data interoperable.
3.4 Increase data re-use (through clarifying licences)	The report is only intended for internal use in FarFish.
4. Allocation of resources	No additional cost required.
5. Data security	Data security provided by the technical support of FarFish website.
6. Ethical aspects	No ethical aspects.
7. Other	NA

1. Data set reference/name	<p><i>Two fish in a pod. Data from a self-sampling pilot program to separate between black hake species in W-Africa</i></p> <p>Blanco-Fernandez, Carmen; Erzini, Karim; Rodriguez-Diego, Sara; Alba-Gonzalez, Pablo; Thiam, Ndiaga; Sow, Fambaye Ngom; Diallo, Mamadou; Viðarsson, Jónas R.; Fernandez-Vidal, Duarte; Goncalves, Jorge M.S.; Rangel, Mafalda; Stobberup, Kim; Garcia-Vazquez, Eva; Machado-Schiaffino, Gonzalo</p> <p>FarFish WP2 (Task 2.)</p> <p>Senegal and Mauritania case studies</p>
2. Data summary	Data from self-sampling pilot trial in Senegal and Mauritanian waters where two species of black hake were separated manually onboard fishing vessels and the results then validated by genetic analysis.
3. FAIR Data	
3.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata	The dataset in excel format has been uploaded to Zenodo https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6363365
3.2 Making data openly accessible	The dataset in excel format has been uploaded to Zenodo https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6363365
3.3 Making data interoperable	The dataset in excel format has been uploaded to Zenodo https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6363365
3.4 Increase data re-use (through clarifying licences)	The dataset in excel format has been uploaded to Zenodo https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6363365
4. Allocation of resources	NA
5. Data security	Data uploaded to Zenodo and the data does also reside on a secure server that is backed-up on a regularly basis.
6. Ethical aspects	NA
7. Other	The samples were collected as part of pilot self-sampling programme. Fishermen from the EU fleet and Senegalese national fleet collected the samples on voluntary basis and the samples were then validated by means of genetic analysis at University of Oviedo. The data is open access and available on Zenodo. The results of the analysis is published in the journal "Frontiers in Marine Science". Name of paper is "Two fish in a pod. Mislabelling on board threatens sustainability in mixed fisheries"

7.2 Appendix 2: Templates

7.2.1 Data Management Plan - Form

1. Data set reference/name	
2. Data summary	
3. FAIR Data	
3.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata	
3.2 Making data openly accessible	
3.3 Making data interoperable	
3.4 Increase data re-use (through clarifying licences)	
4. Allocation of resources	
5. Data security	
6. Ethical aspects	
7. Other	

7.2.2 Data Management Plan - Explanation

1. Data set reference/name	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Identifier for the data set to be produced
2. Data summary	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> State the purpose of the data collection/generation, and explain the relation to the objectives of the project Specify the types and formats of data generated/collected Specify if existing data is being re-used (if any) Specify the origin of the data State the expected size of the data (if known) Outline the data utility: to whom will it be useful
3. FAIR Data	
3.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Outline the discoverability of data (metadata provision) Outline the identifiability of data and refer to standard identification mechanism. Do you make use of persistent and unique identifiers such as Digital Object Identifiers (DOI)? Outline naming conventions used Outline the approach towards search keyword Outline the approach for clear versioning Specify standards for metadata creation (if any). If there are no standards in your discipline, describe what type of metadata will be created and how
3.2 Making data openly accessible	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Specify which data will be made openly available? If some data is kept closed, explain why Specify how the data will be made available Specify what methods or software tools are needed to access the data? Is documentation about the software needed to access the data included? Is it possible to include the relevant software (e.g. in open source code)? Specify where the data and associated metadata, documentation and code are deposited Specify how access will be provided in case there are any restrictions For a useful registry of possible data repositories, see: https://www.re3data.org/. Search for repositories by subject, content type or country.
3.3 Making data interoperable	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Assess the interoperability of your data. Specify what data and metadata vocabularies, standards or methodologies you will follow to facilitate interoperability. Specify whether you will be using standard vocabulary for all data types present in your data set, to allow inter-disciplinary interoperability. If not, will you provide mapping to more commonly used ontologies? For suggestions on relevant vocabularies, see: http://vest.agrisemantics.org/ For resources on data and metadata standards, see: http://fairsharing.org
3.4 Increase data re-use (through clarifying licences)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Specify how the data will be licenced to permit the widest reuse possible Specify when the data will be made available for re-use. If applicable, specify why and for what period a data embargo is needed Specify whether the data produced and/or used in the project is useable by third parties, in particular after the end of the project? If the re-use of some data is restricted, explain why Describe data quality assurance processes Specify the length of time for which the data will remain re-usable

4. Allocation of resources	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Estimate the costs for making your data FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable). Describe how you intend to cover these costs • Clearly identify responsibilities for data management in your project • Describe costs and potential value of long term preservation
5. Data security	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Address procedures for data recovery as well as secure storage and transfer of sensitive data
6. Ethical aspects	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • To be covered in the context of the ethics review, ethics section of DoA and ethics deliverables. Include references and related technical aspects if not covered by the former
7. Other	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Refer to other national/funder/sectorial/departmental procedures for data management that you are using (if any)